
MODULATION AND PARSEVAL'S THEOREM FOR WAVELET TRANSFORM AS AN EXTENSION OF FRACTIONAL FOURIER TRANSFORM

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Abstract:

Integral transforms have been wide use to solve various ordinary and partial differential equations or problems in pure and applied mathematics. Wavelet Transform and Fractional Fourier transform has many applications in signal and image processing.

This paper describes the scaling, modulation and Parseval's theorem of Wavelet Transform as an extension of Fractional Fourier transform.

Keywords: *Fractional Fourier Transform, Wavelet Transform, Extended Wavelet Transform.*

Introduction:

Integral Transform was successfully used for almost 2 century years for solving many problems in mathematics[6]. There are many integral transforms have been used for solving differential equations[8]. The fractional Fourier analysis is used for investigations of fractal structures; which in turn are used to analyze different physical phenomena[2]. The ordinary Fourier transform and related techniques have importance in many areas of science, engineering and technology[10]. The Fourier transform is best mathematical tool used in differential equations, physical

optics, signal and image processing and so on[1,4].

The concept of wavelet started to appeared in the literature only in the 19th century 8th decade that used by Morlet(1982)[3,9]. A French geophysical engineering first introduced the idea of wavelet transform as the mathematical tool for signal and image processing[5]. The wavelet transform decomposes a signal into the representation that shows signal details and tends as a function of time[8]. The kernel of fractional Fourier transform and wavelet transform are closely related to each other so Sharma and bhosale introduce the Wavelet transform as an

extension of fractional Fourier transform[7]. so we are going to discuss modulation and Parseval's theorem for Wavelet transform as an extension of fractional Fourier transform.

Preliminaries:

Wavelet Transform as an extension of Fractional Fourier Transform[7]:

The Wavelet transform as the extension of fractional Fourier transform of $f(x) \in E(R^n)$ is denoted by $W(f(x))(\xi)$ and defined by,

$$W(f(x))(a, b) = W(f(x))(\xi) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} BC_{1\alpha} f(x) e^{iC_{2\alpha}[(x^2 + \xi^2)\cos\alpha - 2x\xi]} dx$$

Where, $b = \xi \sec\alpha$, $a = \tan^{\frac{1}{2}} \alpha$, $B = \frac{e^{\frac{i}{2}b^2 \sin^2 \alpha}}{C(\alpha)|a|^n}$, $C(\alpha) = \frac{e^{\frac{i\alpha}{2}}}{(2\pi i \sin\alpha)^{\frac{1}{2}}}$, $C_{2\alpha} = \frac{1}{2\sin\alpha}$, $C_{1\alpha} = (2\pi i \sin\alpha)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \exp\left(\frac{i\alpha}{2}\right)$, $0 \leq \alpha < \frac{\pi}{2}$.

Testing Function Space $E(R^n)$:

An infinitely differentiable complex valued function f on R^n belongs to $E(R^n)$ if for each compact set $X \subset S_\beta$ where $S_\beta = \{y \in R^n: |y| \leq \beta, \beta > 0\}$

Extended Wavelet Transform of

Translation [8]:

$$W(f(x - x_0))(\xi) = e^{iC_{2\alpha}[x_0^2 \cos\alpha - 2x_0\xi]} W\left(e^{(2iC_{2\alpha}x_0 \cos\alpha)x} f(x)\right)(\xi)$$

Differentiation of Extended Wavelet Transform[8]:

$$D^n W(f(x))(\xi) = \frac{d^n}{d\xi^n} W(f(x))(\xi) = W\left(\sum_{h=0}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor} C_h C_{\alpha,h}(\xi \cos\alpha - x)^{n-2h} f(x)\right)(\xi)$$

Where,

$$C_h = \frac{n!}{(n-2h)!h!} (i)^{n-h} (2)^{n-2h}, C_{\alpha,h} = (C_{2\alpha})^{n-h} \cos^h \alpha$$

Scaling Property of Wavelet Transform as an Extension of Fractional Fourier Transform:

$$W(f(ax))(\xi) = \frac{1}{a} W\left(e^{-iC_{2\alpha}\left[\left(\frac{a^2-1}{a^2}\right)x^2 - 2\left(\frac{a-1}{a}\right)x\xi\right]} f(x)\right)(\xi)$$

Proof: We Know that,

$$W(f(x))(\xi) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} BC_{1\alpha} f(x) e^{iC_{2\alpha}[(x^2 + \xi^2)\cos\alpha - 2x\xi]} dx$$

$$W(f(ax))(\xi) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} BC_{1\alpha} f(ax) e^{iC_{2\alpha}[(x^2 + \xi^2)\cos\alpha - 2x\xi]} dx$$

$$= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} BC_{1\alpha} f(x') e^{iC_{2\alpha}\left[\left(\frac{x'}{a}\right)^2 + \xi^2\right]\cos\alpha - 2\left(\frac{x'}{a}\right)\xi} \frac{dx'}{a}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \\
 &\frac{1}{a} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} BC_{1\alpha} f(x') e^{iC_{2\alpha} \left[\left(1 - \frac{a^2-1}{a^2}\right) x'^2 + \xi^2 \right] \cos\alpha - 2 \left(1 - \frac{a-1}{a}\right) x' \xi} dx' \\
 &= \\
 &\frac{1}{a} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} BC_{1\alpha} f(x) e^{iC_{2\alpha} \left[\left(1 - \frac{a^2-1}{a^2}\right) x^2 + \xi^2 \right] \cos\alpha - 2 \left(1 - \frac{a-1}{a}\right) x \xi} dx \\
 &= \\
 &\frac{1}{a} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} BC_{1\alpha} f(x) e^{iC_{2\alpha} [(x^2 + \xi^2) \cos\alpha - 2x\xi]} e^{iC_{2\alpha} \left[\left(\frac{a^2-1}{a^2}\right) x^2 - 2 \left(\frac{a-1}{a}\right) x \xi \right]} dx \\
 &W(f(ax))(\xi) \\
 &= \frac{1}{a} W \left(e^{-iC_{2\alpha} \left[\left(\frac{a^2-1}{a^2}\right) x^2 - 2 \left(\frac{a-1}{a}\right) x \xi \right]} f(x) \right) (\xi)
 \end{aligned}$$

Modulation of Wavelet Transform as an Extension of Fractional Fourier Transform:

I.

$$\begin{aligned}
 &W(f(x)\cos ax)(\xi) = \\
 &\frac{1}{2} \left\{ e^{iC_{2\alpha} \left[\left(\frac{a\xi}{C_{2\alpha}} - \frac{a^2}{C_{2\alpha}^2}\right) \cos\alpha \right]} W(f(x)) \left(\xi - \frac{a}{2C_{2\alpha}} \right) + \right. \\
 &e^{iC_{2\alpha} \left[\left(-\frac{a\xi}{C_{2\alpha}} - \frac{a^2}{C_{2\alpha}^2}\right) \cos\alpha \right]} W(f(x)) \left(\xi + \frac{a}{2C_{2\alpha}} \right) \left. \right\}
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof:

$$\begin{aligned}
 &W(f(x)\cos ax)(\xi) = \\
 &\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} BC_{1\alpha} e^{iC_{2\alpha} [(x^2 + \xi^2) \cos\alpha - 2x\xi]} f(x) \cos ax \, dx \\
 &= \\
 &\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} BC_{1\alpha} e^{iC_{2\alpha} [(x^2 + \xi^2) \cos\alpha - 2x\xi]} f(x) \left(\frac{e^{iax} + e^{-iax}}{2} \right) dx \\
 &=
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\frac{1}{2} \left\{ \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} BC_{1\alpha} e^{iC_{2\alpha} [(x^2 + \xi^2) \cos\alpha - 2x\xi]} f(x) e^{iax} dx + \right. \\
 &\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} BC_{1\alpha} e^{iC_{2\alpha} [(x^2 + \xi^2) \cos\alpha - 2x\xi]} f(x) e^{-iax} dx \left. \right\} \\
 &= \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} BC_{1\alpha} e^{iC_{2\alpha} [(x^2 + \xi^2) \cos\alpha - 2x \left(\xi - \frac{a}{2C_{2\alpha}}\right)]} f(x) dx \right. \\
 &+ \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} BC_{1\alpha} e^{iC_{2\alpha} [(x^2 + \xi^2) \cos\alpha - 2x \left(\xi + \frac{a}{2C_{2\alpha}}\right)]} f(x) dx \left. \right\} \\
 &= \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} BC_{1\alpha} e^{iC_{2\alpha} \left[\left(x^2 + \left(\xi - \frac{a}{2C_{2\alpha}}\right)^2\right) \cos\alpha - 2x \left(\xi - \frac{a}{2C_{2\alpha}}\right) \right]} f(x) e^{iC_{2\alpha} \left[\left(\frac{a\xi}{C_{2\alpha}} - \frac{a^2}{C_{2\alpha}^2}\right) \cos\alpha \right]} dx \right. \\
 &+ \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} BC_{1\alpha} e^{iC_{2\alpha} \left[\left(x^2 + \left(\xi + \frac{a}{2C_{2\alpha}}\right)^2\right) \cos\alpha - 2x \left(\xi + \frac{a}{2C_{2\alpha}}\right) \right]} f(x) e^{iC_{2\alpha} \left[\left(-\frac{a\xi}{C_{2\alpha}} - \frac{a^2}{C_{2\alpha}^2}\right) \cos\alpha \right]} dx \left. \right\} \\
 &= \frac{1}{2} \left\{ e^{iC_{2\alpha} \left[\left(\frac{a\xi}{C_{2\alpha}} - \frac{a^2}{C_{2\alpha}^2}\right) \cos\alpha \right]} W(f(x)) \left(\xi - \frac{a}{2C_{2\alpha}} \right) \right. \\
 &+ e^{iC_{2\alpha} \left[\left(-\frac{a\xi}{C_{2\alpha}} - \frac{a^2}{C_{2\alpha}^2}\right) \cos\alpha \right]} W(f(x)) \left(\xi + \frac{a}{2C_{2\alpha}} \right) \left. \right\}
 \end{aligned}$$

II.

$$\begin{aligned}
 &W(f(x)\sin ax)(\xi) = \\
 &\frac{1}{2i} \left\{ e^{iC_{2\alpha} \left[\left(\frac{a\xi}{C_{2\alpha}} - \frac{a^2}{C_{2\alpha}^2}\right) \cos\alpha \right]} W(f(x)) \left(\xi - \frac{a}{2C_{2\alpha}} \right) - \right. \\
 &e^{iC_{2\alpha} \left[\left(-\frac{a\xi}{C_{2\alpha}} - \frac{a^2}{C_{2\alpha}^2}\right) \cos\alpha \right]} W(f(x)) \left(\xi + \frac{a}{2C_{2\alpha}} \right) \left. \right\}
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof:

$$\begin{aligned}
 &W(f(x)\sin ax)(\xi) = \\
 &\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} BC_{1\alpha} e^{iC_{2\alpha}[(x^2+\xi^2)\cos\alpha-2x\xi]} f(x)\sin ax \, dx \\
 &= \\
 &\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} BC_{1\alpha} e^{iC_{2\alpha}[(x^2+\xi^2)\cos\alpha-2x\xi]} f(x) \left(\frac{e^{iax}-e^{-iax}}{2i}\right) dx \\
 &= \\
 &\frac{1}{2i} \left\{ \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} BC_{1\alpha} e^{iC_{2\alpha}[(x^2+\xi^2)\cos\alpha-2x\xi]} f(x) e^{iax} dx - \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} BC_{1\alpha} e^{iC_{2\alpha}[(x^2+\xi^2)\cos\alpha-2x\xi]} f(x) e^{-iax} dx \right\} \\
 &= \frac{1}{2i} \left\{ \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} BC_{1\alpha} e^{iC_{2\alpha}[(x^2+\xi^2)\cos\alpha-2x(\xi-\frac{a}{2C_{2\alpha}})]} f(x) dx - \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} BC_{1\alpha} e^{iC_{2\alpha}[(x^2+\xi^2)\cos\alpha-2x(\xi+\frac{a}{2C_{2\alpha}})]} f(x) dx \right\} \\
 &= \frac{1}{2i} \left\{ \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} BC_{1\alpha} e^{iC_{2\alpha}[(x^2+(\xi-\frac{a}{2C_{2\alpha}})^2)\cos\alpha-2x(\xi-\frac{a}{2C_{2\alpha}})]} f(x) e^{iC_{2\alpha}[(\frac{a\xi}{C_{2\alpha}}-\frac{a^2}{C_{2\alpha}^2})\cos\alpha]} dx - \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} BC_{1\alpha} e^{iC_{2\alpha}[(x^2+(\xi+\frac{a}{2C_{2\alpha}})^2)\cos\alpha-2x(\xi+\frac{a}{2C_{2\alpha}})]} f(x) e^{iC_{2\alpha}[(\frac{-a\xi}{C_{2\alpha}}-\frac{a^2}{C_{2\alpha}^2})\cos\alpha]} dx \right\} \\
 &= \frac{1}{2i} \left\{ e^{iC_{2\alpha}[(\frac{a\xi}{C_{2\alpha}}-\frac{a^2}{C_{2\alpha}^2})\cos\alpha]} W(f(x)) \left(\xi - \frac{a}{2C_{2\alpha}} \right) - e^{iC_{2\alpha}[(\frac{-a\xi}{C_{2\alpha}}-\frac{a^2}{C_{2\alpha}^2})\cos\alpha]} W(f(x)) \left(\xi + \frac{a}{2C_{2\alpha}} \right) \right\}
 \end{aligned}$$

Parseval's Theorem for Wavelet Transform as an Extension of Fractional Fourier Transform:

i)

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(x)\overline{g(x)} \, dx = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} W(f(x))(\xi) \overline{W(g(x))(\xi)} \, d\xi$$

ii)

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |f(x)|^2 \, dx = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |W(f(x))(\xi)|^2 \, d\xi$$

Proof:

i) Let,

$$W(g(x))(\xi) =$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} BC_{1\alpha} e^{iC_{2\alpha}[(x^2+\xi^2)\cos\alpha-2x\xi]} g(x) dx$$

By using inverse formula,

$$g(x)$$

$$= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \overline{BC_{1\alpha}} e^{-iC_{2\alpha}[(x^2+\xi^2)\cos\alpha-2x\xi]} W(g(x))(\xi) d\xi$$

$$= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} BC_{1\alpha} e^{iC_{2\alpha}[(x^2+\xi^2)\cos\alpha-2x\xi]} \overline{W(g(x))(\xi)} d\xi$$

Now consider,

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(x)\overline{g(x)} \, dx$$

$$= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(x) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} BC_{1\alpha} e^{iC_{2\alpha}[(x^2+\xi^2)\cos\alpha-2x\xi]} \overline{W(g(x))(\xi)} d\xi \, dx$$

$$= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \overline{W(g(x))(\xi)} \left(\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} BC_{1\alpha} e^{iC_{2\alpha}[(x^2+\xi^2)\cos\alpha-2x\xi]} f(x) \, dx \right) d\xi$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(x)\overline{g(x)} \, dx = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} W(f(x))(\xi) \overline{W(g(x))(\xi)} \, d\xi$$

$$\text{ii) } \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |f(x)|^2 \, dx = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(x)\overline{f(x)} \, dx$$

$$= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} W(f(x))(\xi) \overline{W(f(x))(\xi)} \, d\xi$$

$$= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |W(f(x))(\xi)|^2 \, d\xi$$

Conclusion:

This paper presents scaling, modulation and Parseval's theorem for Wavelet transform as an extension of fractional Fourier transform and this are useful to solve ordinary differential

equations and partial differential equations like heat equation, schrodinger's equation etc.

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